

RATE OF EXERCISE PARTICIPATION AND BLOOD PRESSURE AT REST AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS OF IGNATIUS AJURU UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION, PORT HARCOURT, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study investigated the rate of exercise participation and blood pressure at rest among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Five objectives, five research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised of all undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, the postgraduate students were excluded from the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed with a reliability coefficient of 0.71. Data was analysed on SPSS using frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The findings of the study showed the rate of exercise participation among the students is 68.0%. The mean systolic blood pressure was 126.28mmHg and 118.53mmHg among the male and female students respectively. The mean diastolic blood pressure was 84.50mmHg and 83.02mmHg among male and female students respectively. The tested hypotheses revealed exercise was significant and negatively correlated systolic ($r = -0.311$; $p = 0.000$) and diastolic ($r = -0.312$; $p = 0.000$) blood pressures. The following recommendations were made; parents and guardians should encourage their wards to increase their activity level while maintaining their academic pursuits to improve their physical fitness and overall wellbeing; furthermore, University authorities should develop and strengthen structured physical activity and recreational programs aimed at increasing student participation in regular exercise through organized sports, fitness classes, and campus wellness initiatives.*

Introduction

Regular exercise is widely acknowledged as a key factor in determining cardiovascular health and

general wellbeing. Regular participation in exercise is crucial for managing and preventing non-communicable diseases, including

hypertension, which is still a major global public health issue (World Health Organization, 2024; Dhuli et al., 2022). Hypertension is a chronic medical condition characterized by a sustained elevation of arterial blood pressure above normal physiological levels. It occurs when the force exerted by circulating blood against the walls of the arteries remains consistently high, thereby increasing the workload of the heart and blood vessels. The World Health Organization (2025) recognizes blood pressure values below 140/90 mmHg as generally within the non-hypertensive range, although optimal cardiovascular health is associated with readings closer to 120/80 mmHg. Clinically, hypertension is commonly defined as a systolic blood pressure of 140 mmHg or higher and/or a diastolic blood pressure of 90 mmHg or higher, measured on at least two separate occasions under resting conditions (World Health Organization, 2025).

Systolic blood pressure refers to the maximum pressure exerted by circulating blood on the walls of the arteries during the contraction phase of the heart, known as systole. This occurs when the left ventricle contracts and pumps oxygenated blood into the aorta and systemic circulation. Systolic pressure therefore reflects the force generated by the heart during each heartbeat and is influenced by factors such as cardiac output, arterial stiffness, and vascular resistance (American Heart Association, 2022). Diastolic blood pressure, on the other hand, is the minimum pressure within the arteries when the heart relaxes between beats, a phase known as diastole. During this period, the heart chambers refill with blood while the arterial

walls maintain residual pressure to ensure continuous blood flow throughout the body. Diastolic pressure reflects peripheral vascular resistance and arterial elasticity (World Health Organization, 2025). More recent clinical guidelines classify hypertension beginning at 130/80 mmHg (Lamprea-Montealegre et al., 2018), reflecting evidence linking lower blood pressure thresholds with increased cardiovascular risk.

Hypertension is often referred to as a “silent condition” because many affected individuals may remain asymptomatic for long periods while progressive damage occurs to vital organs such as the heart, brain, kidneys, and blood vessels (Connolly, 2024; World Health Organization, 2025). Persistent elevated blood pressure significantly increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases, including stroke, coronary heart disease, heart failure, and renal impairment (Oparil et al., 2018; World Health Organization, 2025). Lifestyle factors—including physical inactivity, unhealthy diet, excessive salt intake, obesity, stress, and alcohol consumption—play a major role in the development and progression of hypertension, making it a largely preventable public health problem through behavioural modification and early intervention (American Heart Association, 2017).

Exercise as defined by the American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM, 2021) refers to planned, structured, and repetitive bodily movements performed with the objective of improving or maintaining one or more components of physical fitness. Exercise represents a key component of physical activity

and plays an important role in promoting cardiovascular health, regulating body weight, improving muscular strength and supporting overall physiological functioning. Exercise may be broadly classified according to its primary physiologic focus. Major categories of exercise include aerobic exercises which enhance cardiovascular endurance; strength or resistance training which improves muscular strength and endurance; flexibility exercises which promote joint mobility; balance exercises which enhance stability and coordination; and functional exercises, which improve the performance of everyday movements (National Institute of Health, 2021; Zhang et al., 2023). The type, frequency and intensity of exercise typically vary depending on individual fitness goals, health status, personal preferences and physical capabilities. According to recommendations from the American Heart Association (AHA, 2021), adults should engage in at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic exercise or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic exercise per week, in addition to muscle-strengthening activities on two or more days weekly.

Resting blood pressure serves as an important physiological indicator of cardiovascular function (Parati et al., 2020) and is strongly influenced by lifestyle behaviours, including levels of physical activity, dietary habits, stress, and sedentary patterns (Bruno et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2024). Among young adults, especially undergraduate students, lifestyle transitions associated with academic demands and social changes may substantially affect exercise habits and cardiovascular health

outcomes. The undergraduate population represents a critical group for studying health behaviours because habits formed during this developmental stage often persist into adulthood. University students frequently experience reduced physical activity due to academic workload, prolonged sitting, irregular schedules, and increased screen time (Guerriero et al., 2025; Edelmann et al., 2022). These behavioural patterns may predispose students to elevated resting blood pressure even at a relatively young age, thereby increasing future risk for hypertension and other cardiovascular diseases. Conversely, consistent engagement in exercise has been shown to improve vascular function, enhance cardiac efficiency, and promote autonomic balance, which collectively contribute to lower resting blood pressure levels (Green & Smith, 2018; Königstein et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2022).

Earlier studies have established that regular aerobic and resistance exercises can reduce systolic and diastolic blood pressure through mechanisms such as improved endothelial function, reduced peripheral vascular resistance, and enhanced metabolic regulation (Schroeder et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2024). It is on this premise that the researchers sought to investigate the rate of exercise participation and the blood pressure at rest among undergraduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the rate of exercise participation and blood pressure at rest among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port

Harcourt, Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study were to;

1. Assess the rate of exercise participation among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.
2. Determine the mean systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.
3. Evaluate the mean diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.
4. Determine the correlation between exercise participation and systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.
5. Assess the correlation between exercise participation and diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the rate of exercise participation among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt?
2. What is the mean systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt?
3. What is the mean diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt?
4. What is the correlation between exercise participation and systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius

Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt?

5. What is the correlation between exercise participation and diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were stated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant correlation between exercise participation and systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.
2. There is no significant correlation between exercise participation and diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.

Materials and Methods

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design. The study was carried out in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Rivers State. It is a state-owned university located in Rivers State, one of the states in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The study population comprised all undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt with an estimated population of about 21,000 students (ICT, IAUE, 2023). A sample size of 200 students was used for the study. A multistage sampling technique was used for sample distribution. The first stage involved the random selection of four faculties from the seven faculties in the institution. Then one

department from each of the selected faculties was randomly chosen. Then 50 students from each of the selected four departments were randomly recruited to participate in the study. A self-developed questionnaire with a reliability index of 0.71 was used to elicit information from the respondents. Data collected was analysed using frequencies, mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Mean Systolic Blood Pressure among Undergraduate Students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

Gender	Mean Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)
Male	126.28
Female	118.53
Aggregate	120.55

Table 1 presents the result on the mean systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. The result showed that the mean systolic blood pressure among male

Table 2: Mean Diastolic Blood Pressure among Undergraduate Students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

Gender	Mean Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)
Male	84.50
Female	82.49
Aggregate	83.02

Table 2 presents the diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. The result showed that the mean diastolic blood

Results

Rate of regular exercise participation = number of those who participated in exercise regularly ÷ number of those who participated in the study × 100

Rate of exercise participation = $(136 \div 200) \times 100 = 68.0\%$

The rate of exercise participation among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Nigeria was 68.0%

undergraduate students was 126.28mmHg while that of the female undergraduate students was 118.53mmHg. The aggregated mean for the undergraduate students was 120.55mmHg.

pressure among male undergraduate students was 84.50mmHg while that of the female undergraduate students was 82.49mmHg. The

aggregated mean for the undergraduate students was 83.02mmHg.

Table 3: Cross-Tabulation on Correlation between Exercise Participation and Systolic Blood Pressure among Undergraduate Students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

Exercise Participation	Systolic Blood Pressure					
	Low		Normal		High	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
No	3	4.7	14	21.9	47	73.4
Yes	1	0.7	89	85.4	46	33.8
Total	4	2.0	103	51.5	93	46.5

Table 3 presents the summary of cross tabulation on correlation between exercise participation and systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Categorisation of students' systolic blood pressure was done by adopting the American Heart Association (AHA) standardised blood

pressure category. The result showed that 73.4% of undergraduate students that do not participate in exercise had high systolic blood pressure, while 4.7% had low systolic blood pressure. The result further showed that 85.5% of undergraduate students that do participate in regular exercise bouts had normal systolic blood pressure.

Table 4: Cross-Tabulation on Correlation between Exercise Participation and Diastolic Blood Pressure among Undergraduate Students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

Exercise Participation	Diastolic Blood Pressure					
	Low		Normal		High	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
No	3	4.7	10	15.6	51	79.7
Yes	1	0.7	81	59.6	54	39.7
Total	4	2.0	103	51.5	93	46.5

Table 4 presents the summary of cross tabulation on correlation between exercise participation and diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The categorisation of students' diastolic blood pressure was done by adopting the American Heart Association (AHA) standardised blood pressure category. The

result showed that 79.7% of undergraduate students that do not engage in regular exercise had high diastolic blood pressure while 4.7% exhibited low diastolic blood pressure. The result further showed that 59.6% of undergraduate students that engaged in regular exercise had normal diastolic blood pressure while 39.7% had high diastolic blood pressure.

Table 5: Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation between Exercise Participation and Systolic Blood Pressure among Undergraduate Students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

Correlations		Systolic blood pressure	Decision
Participate in exercise	Pearson Correlation (r)	-0.311**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	200	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 presented the summary of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation analysis between exercise participation and systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The result showed that there is a significant negative correlation ($r = -$

0.311; $p = 0.000$) between exercise participation and systolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 alpha level of confidence.

Table 6: Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation between Exercise Participation and Diastolic Blood Pressure among Undergraduate Students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

Correlations		Diastolic blood pressure	Decision
Participate in exercise	Pearson Correlation (r)	-0.312**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	200	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 presents the summary of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation analysis between exercise and diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The result showed that there is a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.312$; $p = 0.000$) between exercise and diastolic blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 alpha level of confidence.

Discussion

The findings of this study provide important insight into the relationship between regular exercise participation and resting blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The reported exercise participation rate of 68.0% reflects a moderate level of physical activity engagement among the students, suggesting a growing awareness of the health benefits of exercise among young adults. This finding contrasts with the study by the World Health Organization (2019), which

reported a high proportion of students who did not engage in exercise thus putting their health at risk. The relatively high participation rate observed in the present study may be linked to the study population's perception of exercise. This aligns with the findings of Kpai and Beleh (2020), who demonstrated that students' perceptions toward exercise significantly influenced their participation levels. However, the segment of students who do not engage in exercise remains a concern, as they may be at increased cardiovascular risk associated with sedentary lifestyles (World Health Organization, 2025).

The results revealed gender differences in resting blood pressure, with male undergraduate students recording a higher mean systolic blood pressure (126.28 mmHg) compared to females (118.53 mmHg). Similarly, males demonstrated a higher mean diastolic blood pressure (84.50 mmHg) than females (82.49 mmHg), while the aggregated mean diastolic pressure was 83.02 mmHg. These findings are consistent with previous studies indicating that males tend to exhibit higher blood pressure levels during early adulthood due to physiological and behavioural factors such as hormonal influences, body composition, and lifestyle differences (American Heart Association, 2022). The male mean systolic value falls within the elevated blood pressure category, suggesting potential early cardiovascular risk. The study findings are consistent with those of Adetunji et al. (2025), who documented a high prevalence of pre-hypertension and hypertension among clinical students at the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. Likewise, Nwoke et al. (2024) reported an increased occurrence of pre-hypertension and hypertension among young adults in Enugu

State. However, the present findings differ from those of Ugochukwu et al. (2020), who recorded mean systolic blood pressure values of 105.8 mmHg and 115.1 mmHg among male and female secondary school students, respectively. This variation may be explained by differences in age and levels of physical activity within the sampled populations.

The distribution of systolic blood pressure according to exercise participation revealed a distinct trend. Among students who did not engage in exercise, 73.4% had elevated systolic blood pressure, while only 21.9% recorded normal levels. Conversely, 85.5% of students who participated in exercise exhibited normal systolic blood pressure values. This observation reinforces existing evidence that regular physical activity enhances cardiac output efficiency and decreases peripheral vascular resistance, thereby promoting lower systolic blood pressure (American College of Sports Medicine, 2021). Similarly, Cornelissen and Smart (2020) documented consistent and significant reductions in blood pressure among individuals who regularly engaged in exercise across diverse populations. Furthermore, Teh et al. (2015) and Kolanowski et al. (2022) reported notable improvements in systolic blood pressure following exercise interventions, underscoring the effectiveness of exercise as a widely applicable non-pharmacological approach to blood pressure management.

A similar trend was observed for diastolic blood pressure. Among non-exercising students, 79.7% had high diastolic blood pressure, compared to 15.6% with normal levels. Conversely, 59.6% of students who exercised regularly recorded normal diastolic blood pressure, although 39.7% still exhibited elevated values. These findings suggest that while

exercise plays a significant role in blood pressure regulation, additional determinants such as dietary habits, psychological stress, sleep quality, and genetic predisposition may also influence diastolic pressure outcomes (National Institutes of Health, 2021).

Correlation analysis further confirmed these observations, revealing a significant negative correlation between exercise participation and systolic blood pressure ($r = -0.311$; $p = 0.000$) and between exercise participation and diastolic blood pressure ($r = -0.312$; $p = 0.000$). These results indicate that increased participation in exercise is associated with reductions in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Studies have shown that regular exercise leads to immediate vasodilation and increased cardiac output, resulting in transient reductions in blood pressure during and after exercise sessions; which often contributes to sustained reductions in blood pressure over time (Cornelissen & Smart, 2020; Kolanowski et al., 2022). Similar relationships have been documented in cardiovascular research, demonstrating that regular exercise induces physiological adaptations such as improved endothelial function, enhanced vascular elasticity, reduced sympathetic nervous system activity, and improved metabolic regulation, all of which contribute to blood pressure reduction (American Heart Association, 2020; World Health Organization, 2025).

Overall, the findings reinforce exercise participation as an effective non-pharmacological strategy for maintaining normal blood pressure and preventing hypertension among young adults. The results highlight the importance of implementing university-based health promotion programs aimed at increasing physical activity

participation, particularly among inactive students.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate a clear relationship between exercise participation and resting blood pressure among undergraduate students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. Although a moderate proportion of students (68.0%) reported participating in exercise, notable differences were observed in blood pressure levels between students who engaged in exercise and those who did not. Male students exhibited higher mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure values compared to female students, suggesting possible gender-related physiological and lifestyle influences on cardiovascular health.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. Parents and guardians should encourage their wards to increase their activity level while maintaining their academic pursuits to improve their physical fitness and overall wellbeing.
2. University authorities should develop and strengthen structured physical activity and recreational programs aimed at increasing student participation in regular exercise through organized sports, fitness classes, and campus wellness initiatives.
3. Regular health education programs should be organized by the Health Educators and University Health centre to educate undergraduate students on the benefits of exercise in preventing hypertension and maintaining healthy blood pressure levels, emphasizing lifestyle modification and early prevention strategies.
4. Periodic blood pressure screening should be introduced within the university health

services to enable early detection of elevated blood pressure and provide timely counselling and intervention for at-risk students.

5. The university management should improve access to safe and well-equipped

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exercise facilities, including gyms, sports fields, and recreational spaces, to encourage consistent participation in physical activity among students.

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